

EARTH OBSERVATION CLIMATE INFORMATION SERVICE

Quick Start Guide

Swansea University Climate High-resolution UK Particu-
late Matter

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1. Quick Start: Swansea University Climate High-resolution UK Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀)

The following will provide you with sufficient information to quickly get to grips with the Swansea University, Climate High-Resolution United Kingdom, Particulate Matter dataset products and to gain some familiarity with the information available.

1.1 What products are available?

These data are produced by a machine learning algorithm that combines inputs from satellite, in-situ and analysis data sources. The algorithm generates measurements of the particulate matter (PM) at sizes smaller than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) and 10 μm (PM₁₀). Original level 2 retrievals in the UK region have been reprojected from the instrument swath onto the Climate High-resolution grid for the UK at 100m resolution and composited over daily and monthly timescales. Two versions of each variable are included: with and without the post-processing filtering that is used in the global AOD dataset that is used as an input.

Product name and acronym	Filename example	Version
SU Daily CHUK Particulate Matter SLSTR L3C	20200522-EOCIS-L3C_PM_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3B-SU_DAILY_CHUK-v1.14.nc	1.14
SU Monthly CHUK Particulate Matter SLSTR L3C	202010-EOCIS-L3C_PM_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3B-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-v1.14.nc	1.14

Table 1 Dataset Products covered in this document

1.2 Summary information

Product Name	SU Daily Particulate Matter SLSTR CHUK L3C
Main observed variable(s)	Particulate Matter $d \leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $d \leq 10 \mu\text{m}$
Geographical range of dataset	$15.37^\circ < \text{lon} < 4.75^\circ$, $47.09^\circ < \text{lat} < 61.14^\circ$
Temporal range of dataset	SLSTR-A: 2016/05/01-2023/12/31 SLSTR-B: 2018/05/09-2023/12/31
Spatial resolution / gridding	100mx100m
Temporal sampling characteristics	Daily
Level of processing	L3C Gridded Data
Dataset citation	doi:10.5285/e6c4000905f346438f4c4c8d674b1637

Table 2 Summary Information for SU Daily PM SLSTR CHUK L3C dataset

Product Name	SU Monthly Particulate Matter SLSTR CHUK L3C
Main observed variable(s)	Particulate Matter $d \leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $d \leq 10 \mu\text{m}$
Geographical range of dataset	$15.37^\circ < \text{lon} < 4.75^\circ$, $47.09^\circ < \text{lat} < 61.14^\circ$
Temporal range of dataset	SLSTR-A: 2016/05-2023/12 SLSTR-B: 2018/05-2023/12
Spatial resolution / gridding	100mx100m
Temporal sampling characteristics	Monthly
Level of processing	L3C Gridded Data
Dataset citation	doi:10.5285/809e67dc32ac4679a5d6a18a35551213

Table 3 Summary Information for SU Monthly PM SLSTR CHUK L3C dataset

1.2.1 Variables summary information

Variable name	Description	Units
x	Easting	m
y	Northing	m
pm2p5_mean	Mean mass concentration of pm ($d \leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) ambient aerosol particles in air	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
pm10_mean	Mean mass concentration of pm ($d \leq 10 \mu\text{m}$) ambient aerosol particles in air	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
pm2p5_fltr_mean	Mean mass concentration with post-retrieval filtering	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
pm10_fltr_mean	Mean mass concentration with post-retrieval filtering	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$

Table 4 Summary information for each variable included in all the datasets.

1.3 What can these products be used for?

These products comprise the start of a long-term dataset of global particulate matter observations. Particulate Matter (PM) consists of tiny particles in the air, made up of various chemical compounds, some of which are toxic. Due to their small size, these particles can enter the bloodstream and affect organs like the heart and brain, leading to serious health issues such as respiratory conditions (e.g., asthma), cardiovascular disease, lung cancer, and potentially dementia, low birth weight, and Type 2 diabetes.

PM is classified by size: PM10 (particles smaller than 10 micrometres) and PM2.5 (finer particles smaller than 2.5 micrometres). PM10 includes PM2.5, so its total mass is always greater. PM data estimates are based mainly on aerosol optical density products, also provided by SU, as well as meteorological variables including boundary layer height, dewpoint temperature, surface pressure and temperature. Aerosol optical depth information was taken from the Swansea University Global

Aerosol retrievals (v1.14) for the Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometers (SLSTR) on the Sentinel-3A and Sentinel-3B satellites. Air quality data was provided for 153 locations in the Automatic Urban and Rural Network (AURN). Meteorological inputs were taken from the ECMWF ERA 5 reanalysis product. Atmospheric composition information was taken from the ECWMF Atmospheric Composition Reanalysis 4 (EAC4) product. Land cover information was provided by MODIS Land Cover products.

1.4 Where to find these products for download

To access the dataset products(s) navigate to the following location:
<https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/a01f32f71c4f424d940aaa4a63fbbec4/>

1.5 Using downloaded data

All data files are provided in NetCDF format and accessible with standard tools. Example python code to ingest, subset, re-grid and display mapped data is given below.

1.5.1 Import Data

This sample code uses the xarray module to import a sample dataset and show the contents.

Example Code:

```
import xarray as xr

# Open a PM Monthly dataset
filename='202007-EOCIS-L3C_PM_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-v1.14.nc'

d=xr.open_dataset(filename)
print(d)
```

Illustrative Results

```
<xarray.Dataset>
Dimensions:          (x: 10970, bnds: 2, y: 15170)
Coordinates:
  * x                (x) int32 -331950 -331850 -331750 ... 764750 764850 764950
  * y                (y) int32 1249950 1249850 1249750 ... -266850 -266950
Dimensions without coordinates: bnds
Data variables:
  x_bnds             (x, bnds) int32 ...
  y_bnds             (y, bnds) int32 ...
  pm2p5_mean        (y, x) float32 ...
  pm10_mean         (y, x) float32 ...
  pm2p5_fltr_mean   (y, x) float32 ...
  pm10_fltr_mean    (y, x) float32 ...
Attributes: (12/41)
  Conventions:      CF-1.6
  naming_authority: uk.ac.su.aatsraerosol
```

```
product_version: 1.0
sensor: SLSTR
platform: Sentinel-3A
resolution: 100m x 100m
...
geospatial_lat_units: metres
geospatial_lon_units: metres
geospatial_lat_resolution: 100
geospatial_lon_resolution: 100
inputfilelist: ['20200701-EOCIS-L3C_PM_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTIN...
summary: This dataset contains the level-3 monthly mea...
```

1.5.2 Data Reduction/Subsetting

This sample code makes a subset of the dataset loaded in the previous subsection, takes a subset and shows the contents of the new data structure.

Example Code:

```
subset=d.pm2p5_mean.sel(x=slice(-10000,5000), y=slice(10000,-7500))
print(subset)
```

Illustrative Results:

```
<xarray.DataArray 'pm2p5_mean' (y: 175, x: 150)>
[26250 values with dtype=float32]
Coordinates:
  * x          (x) int32 -9950 -9850 -9750 -9650 -9550 ... 4650 4750 4850 4950
  * y          (y) int32 9950 9850 9750 9650 9550 ... -7150 -7250 -7350 -7450
Attributes:
  long_name:      Particulate matter d <= 2.5 um
  standard_name:  mass_concentration_of_pm2p5_ambient_aerosol_particles_in_air
  units:          ug m**-3
```

1.5.3 Re-Gridding/Formatting

This code takes the subset formed in the previous subsection, performs a coarsening by binning at 4 times the previous resolution and then shows the resulting data structure.

Example Code:

```
# Regridding to a coarser spatial resolution (4x coarser)
subset_coarse = subset.coarsen(x=4, y=4, boundary='pad').mean()
print(subset_coarse)
```

Illustrative Results:

```
<xarray.DataArray 'pm2p5_mean' (y: 44, x: 38)>
array([[19.439604, 19.098227, 19.66491 , ..., 20.045385, 20.021898,
        20.127277],
       [20.291943, 20.12629 , 20.183052, ..., 20.187864, 20.17245 ,
```

```

    20.254667],
    [20.745174, 21.403563, 22.394926, ..., 20.920895, 22.135132,
     23.912079],
    ...,
    [20.362997, 20.362997, 20.829319, ..., 20.369362, 20.53357 ,
     20.525734],
    [20.362997, 20.398869, 20.936932, ..., 19.806217, 19.806217,
     19.986095],
    [20.362997, 20.554308, 20.936932, ..., 19.806217, 19.806217,
     19.806217]], dtype=float32)
Coordinates:
  * x          (x) float64 -9.8e+03 -9.4e+03 -9e+03 ... 4.2e+03 4.6e+03 4.9e+03
  * y          (y) float64  9.8e+03  9.4e+03  9e+03 ... -6.6e+03 -7e+03 -7.35e+03
Attributes:
  long_name:      Particulate matter d <= 2.5 um
  standard_name:  mass_concentration_of_pm2p5_ambient_aerosol_particles_in_air
  units:          ug m**-3

```

1.5.4 Forming a Time-series

The data files do not contain a time dimension, but this can be deduced either from the file names or the metadata. The following code uses the numpy, xarray and matplotlib modules to read the 12 monthly data files for year, add a time dimension and then plot the mean AOD within a geographic sub-region against time.

Example Code:

```

import xarray as xr
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Set the year and filename parameters
yyyy='2021'
filebase='-EOCIS-L3C_PM_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-v1.14.nc'

# Loop over months in the year
for m in np.arange(1,13):
    # Create the filename for this month
    mm="{:02d}".format(m)
    filename=yyyy+mm+filebase
    # Load the file
    d = xr.open_dataset(filename)
    #Add a "month" dimension of length 1 and make it a coordinate with this month's
    value
    d=d.expand_dims(dim={"Month": 1 } )
    d=d.assign_coords(Month=("Month", [m] ) )
    #Append the new data along the Month dimension
    if (m == 1):
        d_total=d
    else:
        d_total=xr.combine_by_coords([d_total, d],combine_attrs='drop_conflicts')
#End the month loop

```

```
#Find the mean value of AOD across the spatial dimensions
pmvTime=d_total.pm2p5_mean.mean(dim=["x","y"])

#Make a figure and assign month names to the x-axis
fig=plt.figure()
ax=fig.add_subplot(1,1,1)
pmvTime.plot()
mnths=["Jan","Feb","Mar","Apr","May","Jun","Jul","Aug","Sep","Oct","Nov","Dec"]
ax.set_xticks(range(1,13),mnths)
plt.title("Mean SLSTR-A PM2.5 in the UK region during 2021")
```


Figure 1 Time-series of mean PM2.5 in the UK region during 2021 from SLSTR-A data

1.5.5 Displaying Data

This code makes use of the matplotlib and netCDF4 python modules to produce a map of the monthly dataset.

Example Code:

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import netCDF4

# Load the data using the netCDF interface
filename='201806-EOCIS-L3C_PM_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-v1.14.nc'
```

```
pm=netCDF4.Dataset(filename).variables['pm2p5_mean'][:]

# Increase the default font size and lighten the colour mapping
plt.rcParams.update({'font.size': 12})
cmap = plt.get_cmap('jet')

# Create the plotting area
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10,7))
ax=fig.add_subplot(1,1,1)
ax.set_title('SLSTR-A Monthly Mean PM2.5 2018-06')

# Add the data to the map
im=ax.imshow(pm, vmin=0.0, vmax=30.0, cmap=cmap)
plt.colorbar(im, label='PM2.5 ug m-3',orientation='vertical')

# Display the figure
plt.show()
```


Figure 2 Example Monthly Mean PM2.5 field from SLSTR-A

1.6 Interactive visualisation / data access

The monthly mean PM2.5 data can be visualised interactively through the EOCIS data portal
https://eocis.org/portal/viewer/?layer=pm2p5_mean#

1.7 Your obligations when using these products

By accessing the Swansea University Particulate Matter products, you agree to cite the dataset digital object identifier (doi) and corresponding journal article (in preparation) describing the dataset every time you publish results obtained in whole or in part by use of UK EOCIS products. These citations are given under Summary Information.

The reference to the dataset should mention "created by the UK Earth Observation Climate Information Service". The product name and acronym in Table 1 should be used to avoid confusion and enable traceability.

1.8 Further Information

This data set currently runs up to the end of 2023, starting in May 2016 for SLSTR-A and June 2018 for SLSTR-B.

History of modifications / Change Log

Version	Date	Changes	Person
0.1	10 th Feb 2025	Initial Draft	Iain Bye
1.0	18 th May 2026	Initial Release	Kevin Pearson

Related Documents / Reference Documents

Document	Author	Reference

Acronyms and/or Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Definition
PM	Particulate Matter
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Radiometer

General definitions

Term	Definition